

Satisfaction of Employees Plays an Important Role in the Development of the Company

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Abstract

A company's objective is always induced by high profits and great market share and satisfaction of employees is always being considered as an indispensable element in the procedure of attaining this aim. Meanwhile, employees also endeavor more to perform as per benchmarks of the company to prove their competence. This study is an effort to design a conceptual model for Pakistan's firms that can assess to ensure their continuing success and to figure out the persona of satisfaction of employees that contributes significantly to the development of the company. The study reveals that concept of satisfaction of employees is quite multifarious as it is affected by various factors that often have mingled impact. The detailed analysis of various literatures and formation of a conceptual model showed that the role of employee satisfaction for company development plays a dynamic role in the development of the company. Therefore, it is imperious for organizations to ascertain the requirements of employees to please and ensure operative execution of its objectives and targets.

Keywords: Satisfaction of employees, Company development

Introduction

A company's objective is always induced by high profits and great market share. Therefore, satisfaction of employees is being always considered as an indispensable element in the procedure of attaining this aim. Meanwhile, employees also strive hard to perform well as per benchmarks established by the business to ensure their work quality and to prove their competence. Employee's job satisfaction is thus considered mandatory as it allows them to work with ease without fretting. On the other hand, dissatisfaction of employees in any organization may detain the employees from execution up to their full potential.

Companies mostly don't detain the prominence of employee's satisfaction and this creates scores of hitches throughout their work. These companies are not only weak internally but are failed to introduce innovative goods into the market to outdo their opponents.

Satisfaction of Employees

The idea and evolution of job satisfaction was originated in 1911 by the study of Taylor. Taylor specified that the job earnings, promotion, incentive outlays, appreciation and opportunities are the rewards that are vital for employee satisfaction as this leads to the progress of the company. Various researchers declared employee satisfaction as a necessary factor for the growth of the company. Wiener (1982) highlighted that employee's job satisfaction sets an attitude that is compatible with working environment of the company.

The organizational success is always being associated with the satisfaction of employees by managers. Therefore, in today's fast growing and competitive era, managers focus on the innovative paradigm that includes investment in human capital, technology standards, mended training and recruiting practices, and performance oriented compensations for employees at different level to drive the profitability of the company. Employees with good morale, better workplace and motivation are more dedicated and cooperative and perform extraordinary.

Development of the Company

The impact of satisfaction of employees and company development is much more intricate as the value of the company is subjective to innumerable factors, both external and internal. The external factors are away from company's influence while the internal factors are influenced by company. Satisfaction of employees is an internal aspect that has affected company's performance in numerous case studies. However, this factor is sometimes choked by the sway of external factors, settings and considerations.

This work is an attempt to study and figure out the persona of satisfaction of employees that contributes significantly to the development of the company. The prime objective of the study is to review various studies and to develop a conceptual model or framework for Pakistan as this idea is now much more relevant due to its nature and role on the growth of company.

Literature Review

In this section the significance of satisfaction of employees for the growth of the company will be studied by the review of literature as it is believed that the fictional appendages are necessary to analyze the extended work and to formulate a better conceptual model for a firm.

A lot of extensive work has been done all around the world to understand the relevance of satisfaction of employees for the development of the company in various contexts over the years. However, Herzberg was the one who initiated the concept. Herzberg et al. (1959) established a motivational model for job satisfaction. He piloted a study and categorized the factors that affect the job satisfaction. The author divided the factors into two types, Hygiene aspects and motivation aspects. Hygiene aspects can alter the dissatisfaction of employees into short run motivation but it cannot originate satisfaction. These include work surroundings, administration, and company strategy, excellence of supervision, interpersonal relationships, job security, and salary. However, the motivational aspects have long term effects. These aspects elevate optimism for the job and transform no dissatisfaction into satisfaction. Herzberg also indicated that absence of hygiene factors may enhance the dissatisfaction of the employees.

Ostroff (1992) established the fact that firms with more satisfied employees are more inclined towards effectiveness than those with discontented employees. Similarly, Ryan et al. (1996) explored that employee's self-confidence is related to consequent business success indicators, client contentment, and turnover percentages.

Harter et al. (2002) figured out that satisfaction of employees is significantly correlated with the organizational performance. The authors measured the impact by productivity, employee turnover, profit, employee calamities, and customer satisfaction.

Evans and Jack (2003) highlighted the positive role of satisfaction of on firm's market performance. The impact was inspected through salaries of employee per share while market performance is figured out by company's financial state. Correspondingly, Schneider et al. (2003) analyzed that return on assets (ROA) of a firm and higher pays per share have stronger correlation with higher employee's satisfaction.

Baah and Amoako (2011) described that hygienic features of firm can only create external inclination in workers and they are not strong enough to transform the dissatisfaction into satisfaction while the motivational factors assesses employees to work with credibility with their organization. Baah and Amoakadeclared that the work nature, work recognition and achievements, assigning responsibilities and enhancing opportunities are the essential motivations for employee's grooming and improvement to their value in the organization.

Sell and Clear (2011) studied the reaction of employees in hazardous work settings with more monetary incentives and non-hazardous work settings with low monetary incentives. The study explained various

psychosocial and other working indicators like work place and social sustenance. The results revealed these variables have direct impact on satisfaction of employees. However, an increment in remunerations does not improve the dissatisfaction of employees. The authors explained that availability of supervisors, link with colleagues, creative perspectives, mind openness of workers, knowledge of workers and management interaction with employees are the core indicators for supervision. In addition to this, the results also explained that effective management, enhances the level of satisfaction of employees while it declines due to lack of communication.

Bakotic and Babic(2013) found that better work conditions are critical for employee's job satisfaction as it improves under challenging work settings. Therefore, it is required for the organization to expand the work settings. This will make them equally satisfied with those who work under normal working condition and in return overall performance will increase.

Tariq et al (2013) unveiled different determinants of satisfaction of employees such as work pressure, wages, work stress, and family conflicts due to job forces employees towards dissatisfaction that the company's turnover.

Raziq and Maulabaksh (2015) analyzed the effect of working environment on job satisfaction of employees for Pakistan. The authors underlined that bad working conditions are the restrictive factor for workforce to reveal their proficiencies and achieve packed potential. The study pointed the important aspect of job satisfaction for the company performance as it is imperative for the businesses to realize its significance. The study suggested that future growth of businesses is attainable by considering workplace environment more seriously in the company. This may assess to enhance the motivation and commitment level of their employees.

Bakotic (2016) explored the association between job satisfaction of employee and company performance to empirically determine the link between the two variables. The author attempted to figure out the trend and strength of the link by conducting a survey. The author develops a sample of 40 medium and large sized companies, using 5806 employees as respondents. The results confirmed a clear linkage between job satisfaction of employees and company growth. Although, the relationship was bi-directional with weak intensity. The link between employee's job satisfaction and company progress is stronger than the connection between company progress and employee's job satisfaction. Thus the author stated that that job satisfaction strongly defines business progress.

There are various other studies like Huselid (1995), Chan et al (2000),Koys (2001), Ellinger et al. (2002), Harter et al. (2002),Schneider et al. (2003), Zohir (2007) and Chandrasekar (2011) suggested the existence of positive association of employee's job satisfaction with company development.

After reviewing various national and international studies the proceeding section discusses the main factors that may help to enhance the employee satisfaction and to motivate the workers to work more effectively for the development of the company in Pakistan.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the above literature and discussion on different studies, this develops a conceptual model for Pakistan's firms and highlights major factors to for a tentative conceptual framework. The conceptual model is being presented in the figure 1. The independent variable in this work is the satisfaction of employees and the dependent variable is the company development. The first and left side part of the model highlights the determinants of satisfaction of employees that is affected by job characteristics. These include nature of work, future prospects, management, remuneration, company designation, working environment and work hours.

Second and right side part explains the development of the company. The factors included in the model are productivity, market efficiency, commitment, company turnover, share value, innovation and financial strengthening.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Model for Satisfaction of Employees and Company Development

Discussion

The persistent decline in the deposits and restrictions on credit are believed to have severe effects on the economic growth and development in Pakistan. In addition to this, insufficient accumulation of capital and the bankruptcy practices are further enhancing the production halts which ultimately worsen the economic crisis and increase in unemployment. Thus, the contemporaneous economic status quo of Pakistan is forcing enterprises to avail every single opportunity to assure their market position. Therefore, it is pertinent for managers and leaders to enhance their knowledge about the relevant factors of business and company performance.

The conceptual model focuses on the factors that are considered significant to determine satisfaction of employee to achieve healthier outcomes for the company. These ensure that the employees of the organization are motivated and ready to work without any burden or pressure that may lead to decline in their performance. The benefit of providing satisfaction to employees is thus considered remarkable for both the company and its employees.

The satisfaction of employees reflects in company's performance and it can be seen in the context of productivity and market efficiency. The efficiency of the company stimulates by the loyalty of its workforce. In addition to this, the effectiveness and efficiency of the company enhance customer satisfaction and sales.

Meanwhile, the commitment of the company is considered as the silent feature in market and it is believed that highly motivated working staff does follow the rule. This further improves the public dealings and diaspora of management in the company.

Consequently, it is being observed that this may lead to increase in the value created by company in terms of company's turnover and shareholder worth. The creation of shareholder enhances the probability distribution of future sales revenues. These demands create a need to innovation and technological standards and decipher allocation of resources in the market that affects the firm value and thus financial strengthening is achieved. This aspect strongly contributes to the overall financial situation of the company. In sum, the satisfaction of employees is a core variable for the growth and success of business.

Conclusion

The concept of satisfaction of employees is quite multifarious as it is affected by various factors that often have mingled impact. Meanwhile, satisfaction of employees plays a dynamic role in the development of the company. The detailed analysis of various literatures and formation of a conceptual model showed that the role of employee satisfaction for company development is crucial and strong enough to develop and drive up the company value.

In the contemporary world, management of workforce is a difficult process. Employees are now more competitive and conscious about their rights in the company. Therefore, it is imperious for organizations to ascertain the requirements of employees and to please and ensure operative execution of its objectives and targets. Satisfaction of employees boosts their loyalty, productivity, competence & value. This further improves a sagacity of responsibility in employees which ultimately escalates company success as well as lessens cost that emerges from the dissatisfaction of employees.

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